

International Journal on Artificial Intelligence Tools (IJAIT)

CALL FOR PAPERS
Special Issue on

Intelligent Biomedical Systems

<http://www.worldscientific.com/worldscinet/ijait>

Recent technological advances in medicine have facilitated the development of complex biomedical systems including sophisticated biomedical signal devices and instruments, medical imaging equipment, and computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) tools enabling the better delivery of healthcare services. In parallel, computational intelligence, incorporating neural computing, fuzzy systems, evolutionary computing, and more recently, rough sets, and autoimmune systems have emerged as promising tools for the development, application, and implementation of intelligent systems. In the last ten years, there has been a significant effort in the application of computational intelligent techniques in numerous biomedical systems. These cover applications in medical decision-making, biosignal analysis, and biomedical engineering at large, medical imaging, bioinformatics, and others. All these systems underlie the impact of these technologies in the biomedical domain. The aim of this special issue is to focus on the most recent applications of intelligent systems in medicine.

This special issue will be based on a selected number of papers presented in the 12th IEEE International Conference on BioInformatics and BioEngineering (BIBE), Nov. 11-13, Cyprus (<http://bibe2012.cs.ucy.ac.cy/>) conference. Authors are invited to submit papers expanding their work presented at the BIBE 2012 conference. Moreover, authors who did not present in BIBE but their work falls under this call for papers may submit their manuscripts.

Only original and well-focused papers presenting previously unpublished work will be considered. The review will take place within 5 months and only papers with minor revisions will be accepted.

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SUBMISSION OF MANUSCRIPTS

Manuscripts must be prepared according to the format of IJAIT (<http://www.worldscientific.com/page/ijait/submission-guidelines>) and electronically submitted. When submitting, authors are requested to choose "Intelligent Biomedical Systems" in the manuscript type to indicate that the paper is intended for this special issue.

REVISED DEADLINE FOR SUBMISSION: April 30th, 2013

FINAL DECISION: September 30th, 2013

FIRST REVIEWS DUE: June 30th, 2013

PUBLICATION: November, 2013

*For any further questions, please contact the Guest Editors or the Editor-in-Chief:
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